

Strong coupling of phononic cavity modes in 1D corrugated nanobeam

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Abstract: The interaction of phononic cavities modes in one-dimensional nanobeam based structures is theoretically investigated. The overlapping of two closely spaced phononic cavity modes leads to the formation of symmetric and antisymmetric modes, which can be used for the modulation of the frequency and the quality factors of the propagating cavity modes. In addition, the efficient coupling of cavity modes with the modes of a phononic waveguide connected between the two phononic cavities has been demonstrated. We show that such coupling can be used for route, control and modulate phononic cavity modes over large distances between cavities. This demonstration paves the way to engineering complex on-chip phonons networks utilizing mechanical waves to connect quantum systems as phononic or optomechanical cavities.

I. Introduction

Phononic crystals are periodic composite structures where the elastic and acoustic properties display a periodic variation in space^{1, 2, 3, 4}. They can exhibit band gaps in which the propagation of elastic waves is forbidden whatever is the direction of the incident wave. Such artificial periodic structures enable the design of materials for the manipulation of elastic waves, in particular in the field of signal processing. By introducing linear and point defects in the perfect structure, phononic crystals allow the confinement, guiding or filtering of elastic waves. More generally⁵, tailoring the phononic band structure paves the way to several functionalities, ranging from sound control⁶ to negative refraction and high resolution imaging⁷, or nanoscale thermal transport managing⁸. The concept of

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³ A. Khelif, and A. Adibi, (Eds.). *Phononic Crystals: Fundamentals and Applications*. Springer (2015).

⁴ V. Laude, *Phononic Crystals: Artificial Crystals for Sonic, Acoustic, and Elastic Waves* (Vol. 26). Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG (2015).

⁵ M. Maldovan, *Nature* 503, (2013) 209.

⁶ Cummer, S. A., Christensen, J., & Alù, A. (2016). Controlling sound with acoustic metamaterials. *Nature Reviews Materials*, *1*, 16001.

⁷ Page, J. H. (2016). Focusing of ultrasonic waves by negative refraction in phononic crystals. *AIP Advances*, *6*(12), 121606.

⁸ Davis, B. L., & Hussein, M. I. (2014). Nanophononic metamaterial: Thermal conductivity reduction by local resonance. *Physical review letters*, *112*(5), 055505.

phononic crystals^{9, 10} followed by a couple of years the analogue concept of photonic crystals^{11, 12} for the propagation of electromagnetic waves.

Recently, phononic and photonic properties have been combined into a single platform, then providing a new tool to control light and sound simultaneously. Such artificial materials are termed phoXonic crystals^{13, 14} or opto-mechanical crystals¹⁵. Several materials and nanostructures have been suggested in order to obtain simultaneous photonic and phononic band gaps. Maldovan and Thomas¹⁶ demonstrated this property for an infinite two-dimensional (2D) crystal made of square or hexagonal lattices of holes in silicon. Sadah-Saleh et al.¹⁷ extended this investigation to lithium niobite (LiNbO₃) and considered more general lattices. Bria et al.¹⁸ demonstrated the possibility of absolute phoXonic band gaps using the anisotropy of sapphire in the microwave regime. But, the dominant material platform is the silicon slab drilled with periodic arrays of sub-micrometer holes^{14, 15} or snow-flakes inclusions¹⁹. Similar calculations were also performed for a crystal slab constituted by an array of silicon pillars on a SiO₂ plate²⁰. Indeed, it was shown that holes and stubs elements are favorable to create phononic and photonic band gaps. Following recent advances in nanotechnology fabrication, such nanostructures are currently and precisely manufactured using silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology.

Since the phoXonic crystals have the ability of exhibiting band gaps for phonons and photons, they offer the possibility to design linear and cavity defects in which the confinement of both

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¹¹ E. Yablonovitch, Phys. Rev. Lett. 58 (1987), 2059.

¹² J.D. Joannopoulos, S.G. Johnson, J.N. Winn, & R.D. Meade, *Photonic crystals: molding the flow of light*. Princeton university press. (2011)

¹³ Penneec, Y., Laude, V., Papanikolaou, N., Djafari-Rouhani, B., Oudich, M., El Jallal, S., ... & Martínez, A. (2014). Modeling light-sound interaction in nanoscale cavities and waveguides. *Nanophotonics*, 3(6), 413-440.

¹⁴ Penneec, Y., Rouhani, B. D., El Boudouti, E. H., Li, C., El Hassouani, Y., Vasseur, J. O., ... & Martínez, A. (2010). Simultaneous existence of phononic and photonic band gaps in periodic crystal slabs. *Optics express*, 18(13), 14301-14310.

¹⁵ Mohammadi, S., Eftekhar, A. A., Khelif, A., & Adibi, A. (2010). Simultaneous two-dimensional phononic and photonic band gaps in opto-mechanical crystal slabs. *Optics express*, 18(9), 9164-9172.

¹⁶ Maldovan, M., & Thomas, E. L. (2006). Simultaneous localization of photons and phonons in two-dimensional periodic structures. *Applied Physics Letters*, 88(25), 251907.

¹⁷ Sadat-Saleh, S., Benchabane, S., Baida, F. I., Bernal, M. P., & Laude, V. (2009). Tailoring simultaneous photonic and phononic band gaps. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 106(7), 074912.

¹⁸ Bria, D., Assouar, M. B., Oudich, M., Penneec, Y., Vasseur, J., & Djafari-Rouhani, B. (2011). Opening of simultaneous photonic and phononic band gap in two-dimensional square lattice periodic structure. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 109(1), 014507.

¹⁹ Safavi-Naeini, A. H., Hill, J. T., Meenehan, S., Chan, J., Gröblacher, S., & Painter, O. (2014). Two-dimensional phononic-photonic band gap optomechanical crystal cavity. *Physical review letters*, 112(15), 153603.

²⁰ Penneec, Y., Rouhani, B. D., El Boudouti, E. H., Li, C., El Hassouani, Y., Vasseur, J. O., ... & Martínez, A. (2010). Simultaneous existence of phononic and photonic band gaps in periodic crystal slabs. *Optics express*, 18(13), 14301-14310.

excitations²¹ or the existence of slow acoustic and electromagnetic waves²² has been demonstrated. Therefore, several theoretical and experimental works were devoted during the last years to optomechanical interaction in different structures based on well designed cavities. In particular, let us mention the acousto-optic interaction in different cavities inside 2D infinite phoXonic crystals²³,²⁴, at the surface of a 2D crystal²⁵ or in crystal slabs^{26, 27, 28}. The enhancement of photon-phonon interaction has also been investigated in 1D strip waveguide^{29, 30}. In particular, we proposed a new structure consisting of a corrugated nanobeam containing an array of holes in the middle and an array of rectangular stubs on the side^{31, 32, 33, 34}. This structure presents the key advantage to manage almost independently the photonic properties using the holes size and spacing and the phononic ones by the stubs geometry. We demonstrated³³ that this structure, properly designed, can produce the excitation of acoustic modes at 4 GHz, inside a full phononic band gap, with high mechanical Q -factor.

While canonical cavity optomechanical devices have seen significant development, recent interest now turns to engineering more complex on-chip phonon networks utilizing guided mechanical

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²² Penneç, Y., Rouhani, B. D., El Boudouti, E. H., Li, C., El Hassouani, Y., Vasseur, J. O., ... & Martínez, A. C. (2011). Band gaps and waveguiding in phoxonic silicon crystal slabs. *Chinese Journal of Physics*, 49(1), 100-110.

²³ Rolland, Q., Oudich, M., El-Jallal, S., Dupont, S., Penneç, Y., Gazalet, J., ... & Djafari-Rouhani, B. (2012). Acousto-optic couplings in two-dimensional phoxonic crystal cavities. *Applied Physics Letters*, 101(6), 061109.

²⁴ El-Jallal, S., Oudich, M., Penneç, Y., Djafari-Rouhani, B., Makhoute, A., Rolland, Q., ... & Gazalet, J. (2013). Optomechanical interactions in two-dimensional Si and GaAs phoXonic cavities. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 26(1), 015005.

²⁵ Ma, T. X., Zou, K., Wang, Y. S., Zhang, C., & Su, X. X. (2014). Acousto-optical interaction of surface acoustic and optical waves in a two-dimensional phoxonic crystal hetero-structure cavity. *Optics express*, 22(23), 28443-28451.

²⁶ Gavartin, E., Braive, R., Sagnes, I., Arcizet, O., Beveratos, A., Kippenberg, T. J., & Robert-Philip, I. (2011). Optomechanical coupling in a two-dimensional photonic crystal defect cavity. *Physical review letters*, 106(20), 203902.

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²⁸ El-Jallal, S., Oudich, M., Penneç, Y., Djafari-Rouhani, B., Laude, V., Beugnot, J. C., ... & Makhoute, A. (2013). Analysis of optomechanical coupling in two-dimensional square lattice phoxonic crystal slab cavities. *Physical Review B*, 88(20), 205410.

²⁹ M. Eichenfield, J. Chan, R.M. Camacho, K.J. Vahala, O. Painter, *Nature*, 462 (2009), p. 78

³⁰ J. Chan, A.H. Safavi-Naeini, J.T. Hill, S. Meenehan, O. Painter, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 101 (2012), Article 081115

³¹ Penneç, Y., Rouhani, B. D., Li, C., Escalante, J. M., Martínez, A., Benchabane, S., ... & Papanikolaou, N. (2011). Band gaps and cavity modes in dual phononic and photonic strip waveguides. *AIP advances*, 1(4), 041901.

³² M. Oudich, S. El-Jallal, Y. Penneç, B. Djafari-Rouhani, J. Gomis-Bresco, D. Navarro-Urrios, C.M. Sotomayor Torres, A. Martínez, A. Makhoute, *Phys. Rev. B*, 89 (2014), Article 245122

³³ J. Gomis-Bresco, D. Navarro-Urrios, M. Oudich, S. El-Jallal, A. Griol, D. Puerto, E. Chavez, Y. Penneç, B. Djafari-Rouhani, F. Alzina, A. Martínez, C.M. Sotomayor Torres, *Nat. Commun.*, 5 (2014), p. 4452

³⁴ Djafari-Rouhani, B., El-Jallal, S., & Penneç, Y. (2016). Phoxonic crystals and cavity optomechanics. *Comptes Rendus Physique*, 17(5), 555-564.

waves to connect optomechanical systems^{35, 36, 37}. Realizing on-chip phonon networks requires engineering the phonon modes and the coupling of these modes to each other in a controllable way. We propose here to compose cavities and waveguides in a 1D corrugated silicon nanobeam made of holes and stubs to select, route, and modulate elastic waves. We first define in section 1 the geometrical parameters of a defect inserted in the nanobeam to get the transmission of a phononic cavity mode. Then, in section 2, we propose to connect two identical cavities, playing with the nature of the connected waveguide, to define the conditions for route and modulate the transmission of the cavity modes. The results are qualitatively discussed through an equivalent multilayer method for simple model based on mass density modulation and numerically applied on full three dimensional devices with the help of the finite element method.

1. Single cavity in corrugated nanobeam

1.1. Defect modes in corrugated nanobeam

Figure 1(a) depicts the 3D unit cell which defines the perfect silicon nanobeam composed of holes and stubs. The silicon is considered as a cubic material with the elastic constants $c_{11} = 166$ GPa, $c_{12} = 64$ GPa and $c_{44} = 79.6$ GPa, and a mass density $\rho = 2330$ kg/m³. The geometrical parameters involved in the structure are the pitch $a = 500$ nm, the thickness of the nanobeam $h = 220$ nm ($0.44a$), the hole radius $r = 150$ nm ($0.3a$), and from each side of the nanobeam two rectangular stubs of width $d = 250$ nm ($0.5a$) and length $l = 500$ nm (a). With these geometrical parameters, the calculation of the dispersion curve gives rise to a phononic band gap for symmetric waves in the frequency range [1.76, 2.24] GHz, as reported in [31].

We then define a finite structure composed of 10 unit cells in which we introduce a simple defect (figure 1(b)). For the sake of simplification, the definition of the structure will be addressed following the schematic representation - (o)^N x (o)^N - where N is the number of perfect unit cell ‘o’, ‘-’ the nanobeam, and ‘x’ is the symbol of the defect. As seen from figure 1(b), the defect, localized in the middle of the periodic structure can be defined with a period mismatch, δ , between the two centered unit cells and a height mismatch, η , of the two adjacent stubs. The calculation of the transmission (figure 1(c)) is performed with the help of the finite element method (FEM) in COMSOL multiphysics. We assume that the direction of propagation in the nanobeam coincide

³⁵ Fang, K., Matheny, M. H., Luan, X., & Painter, O. (2016). Optical transduction and routing of microwave phonons in cavity-optomechanical circuits. *Nature Photonics*.

³⁶ Patel, R. N., Sarabalis, C. J., Jiang, W., Hill, J. T., & Safavi-Naeini, A. H. (2017). Engineering phonon leakage in nanomechanical resonators. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.07869*.

³⁷ Fang, K., Luo, J., Metelmann, A., Matheny, M. H., Marquardt, F., Clerk, A. A., & Painter, O. (2017). Generalized non-reciprocity in an optomechanical circuit via synthetic magnetism and reservoir engineering. *Nature Physics*.

with the x -axis of the Cartesian coordinates system (O, x, y, z). The incoming wave, launched from the source position, is taken symmetric. To do this, we applied a homogeneous force per area with a longitudinal component along x and a value of 10^8 N/m² at the source plane. From each side of the super cell, perfect matching layers (PML) are applied to avoid any perturbations coming from the boundaries.

Fig. 1 (a) Representation of one unit cell of the corrugated nanobeam where $a = 500$ nm is the lattice parameter, $e = 0.44a$ the thickness of the nanobeam, $r = 0.3a$ the radius of the hole, $d = 0.5a$ and $l = a$ are the width and the length of one rectangular stub respectively. (b) Schematic representation 1D periodic nanobeam with a single defect localized in the middle of the nanobeam and defined by the geometrical parameters δ and η in the $x0y$ plane). (c) Transmittance in logarithm scale at the fixed frequency of 2.053 GHz as a function of the period mismatch, δ , and for three different values of η ,

In the general case, the equations of motion governing the displacement vectors with the components $u_i(\mathbf{r}, t)$ are given by:

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial^2 u_i(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t^2} = \sum_j \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial j} + F_i, \quad (1)$$

where $i = x, y, z$, F_i are the components of the source force per volume, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ is the position-dependent mass density of the system and $\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the stress tensor:

$$\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, t) = c_{ijmn}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial u_m(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial n}, \quad (2)$$

where $c_{ijmn}(\mathbf{r})$ is the position-dependent elastic stiffness tensor of the system. In cubic crystals, when the x -axis coincides with the crystallographic direction [100], Eq. (1) is expressed in the form:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 u_x}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(c_{11} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + c_{12} \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} + c_{12} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} c_{44} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} c_{44} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} \right), \quad (3)$$

while other equations are obtained by a cycling rearranging of the indices.

The transmittance/reflectance curves presented in the paper are calculated with the time-average

Poynting vector ($P_i(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{\partial u_j(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} \sigma_{ji}(\mathbf{r}, t)$). In the frequency domain, the Poynting vector along the x -axis direction can be written as:

$$P_x(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \omega \text{Im} \left(u_x(\mathbf{r}, \omega)^* \sigma_{xx}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) + u_y(\mathbf{r}, \omega)^* \sigma_{yx}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) + u_z(\mathbf{r}, \omega)^* \sigma_{zx}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \right), \quad (4)$$

which becomes, in cubic crystals:

$$P_x(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \omega \text{Im} \left(u_x^* \left(c_{11} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + c_{12} \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) \right) + c_{44} \left(u_y^* \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} \right) + u_z^* \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} \right) \right) \right). \quad (5)$$

The effect of the geometry of the defect is investigated considering a chosen frequency of 2.053 GHz, which falls in the middle of the phononic band gap. We then proceed to the calculation of the transmittance at this specific frequency and modified the geometrical parameters of the defect, namely η and δ . The transmittance is defined as the ratio between the x -components of the Poynting vector averaged over the detection plane for the structure under consideration and a single nanobeam (without holes and stubs). As reported figure 1(c), when $\eta = 0$ (black solid line), one can see the occurrence of periodic peaks when the height δ of the stubs increases. For two other values of η (0.25 (red curve) and 0.50 (green curve)) the peaks shift to the lower frequencies. Practically, it means that the introduced parameters create the condition of cavity modes that can be driven inside the middle of the phononic band gap with high quality factor. A qualitative discussion based on an analogy with an equivalent multilayer model will be first given in the following section (1.2) before coming back to the simulation (section 1.3).

1.2. Equivalent multilayer model

To describe and analyze the effect of the introduction of the phononic cavity modes inside the nanobeam, we have considered an equivalent multilayer structure of mass density, ρ_m and stiffness coefficients $c_{ij}^{(m)}$, where m corresponds to the m^{th} homogeneous layer. In the case of the longitudinal displacement ($u_x \gg u_y, u_z$), the Eq. (3) takes the form:

$$\rho^{(m)} \frac{\partial^2 u_x}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(c_{11}^{(m)} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(c_{44}^{(m)} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(c_{44}^{(m)} \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} \right), \quad (6)$$

and the solution of Eq. (6) can be expressed in the form of superposition of two plane waves in the following form

$$u_m(x, z, t) = \left(C_m^+ e^{ik_x^{(m)}(x-x_m)} + C_m^- e^{-ik_x^{(m)}(x-x_m)} \right) e^{i(k_z z - \omega t)} + c.c., \quad (7)$$

with the longitudinal and transverse components of the wave vector

$$k_x^{(m)} = \frac{2\pi f}{v_m^l} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v_m^t}{v_{eff}^t} \right)^2}, \quad k_z^{(m)} = \frac{2\pi f}{v_{eff}^t} \quad (8)$$

where $v_m^l = \sqrt{c_{11}^{(m)}/\rho_m}$ and $v_m^t = \sqrt{c_{44}^{(m)}/\rho_m}$ are the longitudinal and transverse sound velocities, f the frequency, C_m^\pm are the amplitudes of the plane waves (unknown coefficients), where the sign “+” is associated with waves propagating along the x -axis and “-” in the opposite direction. In the Eq. (8) we introduced the effective transverse sound velocity, v_{eff}^t , for propagating modes. Noting that the condition $v_{eff}^t < v_m^t$ results in a completely imaginary longitudinal component of the wave vector, which means the presence of evanescent waves only, whereas the condition $v_{eff}^t > v_m^t$ results in an entirely real longitudinal component of the wave vector and corresponds to propagating waves.

Taking into account the continuity conditions of the displacement and the normal stress, the unknown coefficients in Eq. (7) can be found from the system of linear equations and presented by the following matrix form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddots & & & & & & \\ 0 & -\Gamma_m & -\Gamma_m^{-1} & 1 & 1 & 0 & \\ 0 & -c_{11}^{(m)}k_x^{(m)}\Gamma_m & c_{11}^{(m)}k_x^{(m)}\Gamma_m^{-1} & c_{11}^{(m+1)}k_x^{(m+1)} & -c_{11}^{(m+1)}k_x^{(m+1)} & 0 & \\ & & & \ddots & & & \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ C_m^+ \\ C_m^- \\ C_{m+1}^+ \\ C_{m+1}^- \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (9)$$

where $\Gamma_m = e^{ik_x^{(m)}(x_{m+1}-x_m)}$. To obtain non-trivial solution of this system of linear equations, at least two coefficients have to be known. For transient problem, we use the condition of incoming waves $C_1^+ = 1$ and $C_N^- = 0$ in the case of N -layer multilayer system, which means that the source with unit amplitude is located in the first medium. In this case, the transmittance is equal to the square of the absolute value of the amplitude of the outgoing plane wave in the final medium

$$T = |C_N^+|^2. \quad (10)$$

To analyze the origin of the peaks obtained figure 1(c) and their behavior as a function of the defect geometry, let us consider a system consisting of three layers of mass densities ρ_1 , ρ_2 and ρ_3 and two interfaces located at the coordinates x_1 and x_2 (figure 2(a)). This simple model sketches the corrugated defect nanobeam, considering bulk waves propagating with the transverse component of the wave vector $k_z^{(m)}$ in Eq. (8). The mass densities are chosen in the way that the centered layer is surrounded by two barriers, in correspondence with a defect cavity between two Bragg mirrors in the nanobeam. In absence of ingoing waves, the localized modes condition can be resolved from the homogeneous linear system of equations (Eq. (9)), leading to the system:

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ c_{11}^{(1)}k_x^{(1)} & c_{11}^{(2)}k_x^{(2)} & -c_{11}^{(2)}k_x^{(2)} & 0 \\ 0 & -\Gamma_2 & -\Gamma_2^{-1} & 1 \\ 0 & -c_{11}^{(2)}k_x^{(2)}\Gamma_2 & c_{11}^{(2)}k_x^{(2)}\Gamma_2^{-1} & c_{11}^{(3)}k_x^{(3)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C_1^- \\ C_2^+ \\ C_2^- \\ C_3^+ \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (11)$$

or in the short form of the denominator of unknown coefficients in the reflection and transmission (RT) matrix method³⁸ notation:

$$\Gamma_2^{-2} + r_{12}r_{23} = 0 \text{ or } e^{-2ik_x^{(m)}x_{21}} = r_{12}r_{32}, \quad (12)$$

³⁸ Xiaofei Chen, A systematic and efficient method of computing normal modes for multilayered half-space, Geophys J Int (1993) 115 (2): 391-409.

where $r_{ij} = -r_{ji} = \frac{c_{11}^{(i)}k_x^{(i)} - c_{11}^{(j)}k_x^{(j)}}{c_{11}^{(i)}k_x^{(i)} + c_{11}^{(j)}k_x^{(j)}}$ is the reflectance at a single interface between two media i and j .

In the case of a symmetric structure composed of three-layer ($\rho_1 = \rho_3$), the condition of mode confinement is $v_2^t < v_{eff}^t < v_1^t$ for which $\rho_2 < \rho_1$. This inequality corresponds to the imaginary longitudinal component of the wave vector in the surrounding regions with the mass density ρ_1 , for which only evanescent waves exist inside such media. And the longitudinal component of the wave vector is real in the middle layer with the mass density ρ_2 . Then the solution of Eq. (12) is expressed analytically in the following form

$$f_{res} = \frac{m + \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan \left(\frac{c_{11}^{(1)}v_2^t}{c_{11}^{(2)}v_1^t} \sqrt{\frac{(v_1^t/v_{eff}^t)^2 - 1}{1 - (v_2^t/v_{eff}^t)^2}} \right)}{\sqrt{1 - (v_2^t/v_{eff}^t)^2} 2x_{21}/v_2^t}. \quad (13)$$

We can estimate the mass density in the framework of effective medium approximation. Then, for the cells with stubs and holes, the mass density can be estimated in the following form $\rho_{eff} = \rho_{Si}\xi + \rho_{air}(1 - \xi)$, where ρ_{Si} is the mass density of silicon, $\rho_{air} \ll \rho_{Si}$ is the mass density in air (or vacuum), ξ is the air/silicon filling factor ($\xi = \pi r^2 / (a^2 + 2hd)$). The transverse sound velocity profile corresponding to mass density in the barrier layers with $\xi = 0.7$ ($v_2^t = v_4^t = v_1^t / \sqrt{\xi}$) and $\xi = 1$ for the rest layers is presented figure 2(a). One can remind that the middle layer of velocity $v_3^t = v_1^t$ corresponds to the nanobeam defect while the two barriers of velocities $v_{2,4}^t$ are associated to the Bragg mirrors of the periodic nanobeam.

Figure 2b shows the transmittance (Eq. (10)) spectrum as a function of the frequency with an effective transverse sound velocity, $v_{eff}^t = 0.9v_1^t = 6488$ m/s ($v_1^t < v_{eff}^t < v_2^t$ because the barrier regions are numbered by 2 and 4 in this case) in the multilayer structure. The spectrum shows that the multilayer structure supports a localized mode around 1.95 GHz. The calculation has been performed with a length of the centered layer $d_c = 2.4$ μ m and for various thicknesses d_b of the barrier layers. As expected, figure 2(b) shows that, increasing the thickness d_b of the barriers leads to an increase of the resonance quality factor due to a reduction of the leakage between the confined cavity mode inside the centered layer and the continuous environment. This conclusion is also

supported by the figure 2(c) which summarizes the evolution of the Q -factor and the resonant frequency as a function of d_b .

Fig. 2 (a) Schematic presentation of 1D periodic nanobeam with a single defect and the corresponding profile of transverse sound velocity for the equivalent multilayer structure (the numbers correspond to the different involved layers). (b) Transmittance of the propagating mode for $d_d = 2.4 \mu\text{m}$ and for $v_{eff}^t = 6488$ m/s ($v_1^t < v_{eff}^t < v_2^t$). (c) Quality factor and position of the resonant frequency as a function of the barrier thickness d_b .

We then proceed to the calculation of the transmission in the frequency range [1.6, 2.5] GHz. The figure 3(a) reports the position of the maximum of the resonance peak, if exist, as a function of the lengths of the centered layer d_c , for a constant value $d_b = 5 \mu\text{m}$ of the barrier thickness. Three modes (black, red, and green solid lines) appear in the diagram for which one can follow the evolution as a function of the size of the defect.

Figure 2b shows the maximum frequency obtained at 1.92 GHz (cyan curve). The corresponding calculation of the displacement field distribution is reported in the inset of the figure. One can see that the mode is symmetric with respect to the middle of the structure. At almost the same frequency ($f = 1.96$ GHz), one can also obtain the antisymmetric mode distribution when length of the centered layer is $d_c = 7 \mu\text{m}$. We also drawn in figure 3(b) the quality factors of the resonant peaks, which decrease as a function of d_c .

Fig. 3 Resonant frequency and Q -factor as a function of the thickness of middle (defective) layer. (Inset): spatial distribution of longitudinal displacement (u_x) for $d_c = 2.4\mu\text{m}$ (left) and $d_c = 7\mu\text{m}$ (right).

1.3. Numerical results

A similar calculation for the corrugated nanobeam with defect sketched figure 1(b) has been done numerically using COMSOL multiphysics. The figure 4 presents the transmission spectrum for the defect geometry $\delta = 0.4 a$, and $\eta = 0.5 a$. As expected from figure 1(b), a single peak appears in the phononic band gap around 2.053GHz, depending on the degree of the localization of the mode. The figure 4(b) reports the evolution of the frequency at the maximum of the peak as a function of the number of unit cells surrounding the defect together with the evolution of the quality factor. One can see that the resonant frequency tends quickly towards a constant value and the quality factor increases as far as the mode becomes more and more isolated from the external media. The higher value of the quality factor is obtained when the defect is surrounded by five perfect unit cells, reaching $25 \cdot 10^3$. We finally present in figure 4(c) the displacement field corresponding to the first and second modes of figure 1(b), respectively according to the longitudinal and transverse components. We do not show the third component of the displacement, since the largest values of this displacement are on the upper and lower surfaces of the nanobeam and the value is much less than the other two components. In agreement with the conclusions done on the equivalent multilayer model, we can see that the two first modes correspond respectively to a symmetric ($m = 1$) and an antisymmetric ($m = 2$) modes, well localized inside the cavity defect.

Fig. 4 (a) Transmittance of the propagating longitudinal mode through the nanobeam with defect of figure 1(a) using the FE method. The dimensions of the defect are $\delta = 0.4a$, and $\eta = 0.5a$, with $a = 500$ nm. The transmission is presented according to the scheme “ $- \mathbf{o}^N \mathbf{x} \mathbf{o}^N$ ”, for different values of N. (b) Quality factor and resonant frequency as a function of N. (c,d) Spatial distribution of the longitudinal and transverse displacements at the resonant frequency 2.053 GHz (left) for $\delta = 0.4a$ (c) and $\delta = 3.95a$ (d).

To summarize, the main conclusions have been obtained from both calculations, i.e. the equivalent multilayer model and the numerical FEM. Such analogy is very helpful for physical understanding and time consuming calculations. Of course, it remains that for comparison with real structures, the FEM calculation is needed, to extract the real values of the frequencies and quality factors. Nevertheless, in the next section, the equivalent multilayer model will be applied to understand the coherent control of the coupling between two cavities. Then, we proceed to the calculation of the real 3D structure using the FEM calculations.

2. Coupled cavities in corrugated nanobeam

After considering the properties of a single phononic cavity inside the nanobeam, let us move to the analysis of the coupling between two phononic cavities. For such purpose, we have considered two structures represented figure 5. In the first one, we link directly the two nanobeams together while in the second, we introduce a straight phononic waveguide between the two nanobeams.

Figure 5: Schematic presentation of the phononic nanobeam including two defects with the schematic representation (a) “- o⁴ x o^N x o⁴ -” and (b) “-o⁴ x o⁴ - o⁴ x o⁴ -”.

We first report the calculation considering the equivalent multilayer model applied on the transverse sound velocity profile (inset of figure 6(a)) which represents the coupling of two closed cavities. In this case, the splitting of the resonant frequencies, f_{\pm} , can be estimated in the framework of tunnel-coupled localized modes in the following form:

$$f_{\pm} = \sqrt{(f_l - f_r)^2 + T^2} \text{ with eigenvectors } c_{\pm} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \pm 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where f_l and f_r are the resonant frequencies of the left and right cavity (*note*: for a same cavity $f_l = f_r \equiv f_0$). In this expression, $T \propto \int_V \mathbf{u}_l^\dagger \mathbf{u}_r dV$ is the tunneling matrix element and $\mathbf{u}_{l,r}$ are the displacement fields. The displacement profile for leaking cavity modes (insets in figure 3) can be divided into two regions: *i*) the region of strong localization (3rd layer in figure 2(a)), with evanescent waves from the center of each cavity (2nd and 4th layers in figure 2(a)), and *ii*) the leakage region (1st and 5th layers in figure 2(a)) with oscillating behavior, proportional to $\sin(k_x(x+x_0))$, where k_x is the wave vector of the propagation mode, and $k_x x_0$ is the phase between the leaked waves. The tunneling matrix element for two cavities in interactions through the barrier (figure 5(a)) can thus be estimated as $T(d) \propto e^{-k_b d}$, since the tunneling matrix element is mainly determined by the overlapping of evanescent waves, where d is the barrier thickness, k_b is the wave vector in the barrier region. When the two cavities are in interactions through the nanobeam (figure 5(b)), the tunneling matrix element can be estimated as $\cos(k_{\text{int}} d)$, as the resulting interaction is mainly determined by the overlapping of localized (see displacement profile of layer 3 of the insets in figure 3) and oscillating functions (layer 1 or 5) in the cavity regions with

a characteristic wave vector, k_{int} associated with the interference between two waveguide modes in the connecting nanobeam.

Considering now the case where the two cavities are connected through the phononic corrugated waveguide. The corresponding transverse sound velocity profile is drawn in the inset of figure 6(a). Three modes are now in interaction, i.e. the two cavity modes and the standing waveguide phononic one. By analogy, the eigen state problem reads as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} f_1 - f & T_{12} & T_{13} \\ T_{12} & f_2 - f & T_{23} \\ T_{13} & T_{23} & f_3 - f \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (15)$$

where T_{ij} is the tunneling matrix element between i^{th} and j^{th} modes. When the three resonant frequencies are the same, ($f_1 = f_2 = f_3 \equiv f_0$), we get the resonant frequency of the system from Eq. (15):

$$f_{\text{res}1} = f_0 - T_{13}, \quad f_{\text{res}2,3} = f_0 + \frac{T_{13} \pm \sqrt{8T_{12}^2 + T_{13}^2}}{2}, \quad (16)$$

with the eigenvectors

$$c_{\text{res}1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad c_{\text{res}2,3} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{4T_{12}^2 - T_{13}(T_{13} \pm \sqrt{8T_{12}^2 + T_{13}^2})}{T_{12}(3T_{13} \mp \sqrt{8T_{12}^2 + T_{13}^2})} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

where T_{12} is the tunneling matrix element between the cavity mode and the standing waveguide mode and T_{13} is the tunneling matrix element between the two cavity modes. For large distance between cavities, T_{13} can be neglected and the resonant frequencies (16) and eigenvectors (17) are determined following:

$$f_{\text{res}1} = f_0, \quad f_{\text{res}2,3} = f_0 \pm \sqrt{2}T_{12}, \quad (18)$$

$$c_{\text{res}1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad c_{\text{res}2,3} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \mp \sqrt{2}T_{12} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

As we can see from Eq.(18) and (19), the coupling between the three layers (cavity/waveguide/cavity) leads to one resonance of the two cavities at f_0 and two others modes

which come from a combination of the 3 involved elements, i.e. the two cavities and the connected waveguide.

The transmission spectrum calculated through a system of two cavities directly connected is presented figure 6(a) for a propagating mode with an effective transverse sound velocity of 6488 m/s. The transmission curve reveals the existence of two peaks respectively at 1.5 and 2.2 GHz for a distance $d = 3 \mu\text{m}$ between the two cavities. We then report figure 6(b) the frequency position of these two peaks as a function of the distance, d , varying from 0.5 to 9 μm . One can see that the two resonant frequencies converge toward a centered frequency $f_0 = 1.92 \text{ GHz}$ when the distance d increases. For large values of d , the two cavities can be considered as independent from each other and do not have any interaction together. It means that, when the two cavities get closer, we progressively raise the degeneracy of the cavity mode at f_0 , which splits, as usual, in a symmetric and an antisymmetric one with respect to the middle plane between the two cavities. The figure 6(b) also reports the behavior of the quality factor: as d decreases, the quality factor of the symmetric (resp. antisymmetric) peak decreases (resp. increases) by at least one order of magnitude. The quality factor for strongly coupled defect modes depends on the symmetry and the distance between the cavities. As a result, the splitting of the cavity mode is possible only when the two cavities are close from each other. Over a distance of a few μm , the two cavities are not connected anymore. It means that the frequency modulations are not yet possible and even more, when the connected acoustic nanobeam becomes too long, the transmission from one cavity to the other becomes less and less efficient due to the lower recovery of the evanescent signals.

Figure 6 (a) Transmittance of the propagating mode with an effective transverse sound velocity of 6488 m/s. The inset presents the transverse sound velocity profile of the structure under consideration. (b) Evolution of the resonance frequency and the quality factor as a function of the distance d between the cavities. (c) Same as (a) for the transverse sound velocity profile in the inset. (d) Evolution of the resonance frequency and the quality factor as a function of the distance D of the connected phononic waveguide. The dashed lines correspond to the resonance position from the analytical expression for three-layers system with transverse sound velocities (in m/s) “6986/5845/6986” corresponding to mass densities (in kg/m³) “2330/1631/2330” (Eq. (13)).

We thus propose another way to both route and modulate the transmission of the cavity modes. As sketched in the inset of figure 6(c), we now introduce a straight phononic waveguide of length D between the two cavities. The corresponding transmission spectrum, reported figure 6(c), is calculated for $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$ (when the two cavities are almost independent from each other), and for $D = 2 \mu\text{m}$. The transmission diagram presents now three peaks whose one is at the frequency of the cavity mode, i.e. 1.917 GHz. In the present device, it becomes possible to excite phononic modes coming from the straight connected waveguide. In this case, the interaction of three localized modes occurs for which the behavior is reported figure 6(d) as a function of the length D of the inserted phononic waveguide. When $D = 0 \mu\text{m}$ and as previously reported, the cavity mode are splitted in symmetric (black solid line) and antisymmetric (red solid line) modes because of the coupling between the two cavities $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$. One can see that, as D increases, the symmetric mode interacts with a new one (green line) for $D = 2.25 \mu\text{m}$ while the antisymmetric mode interacts with another

one (blue line) for $D = 2.8 \mu\text{m}$. These two new modes correspond to the eigenmodes of the connected phononic waveguide. The interaction of the three peaks leads to the splitting of the two which present the same symmetry. The figure 6(d) shows also the variation of the Q -factor of the different modes as a function of D . In the mixing between defect cavity mode and standing waveguide modes, the quality factor can reach values higher than 10^4 . To summarize, using the phononic waveguide eigenmodes, we have been able to route the phononic cavity modes over a long distance and proceed to a modulation of the frequency and the Q -factors of the transmitted cavity modes.

Finally, we transpose the simple model to the numerical calculation of the two 3D nanobeams of figure 5 with the help of the finite element method. The figure 7(a) corresponds to the case where the two cavities are connected by the corrugated nanobeam. The figure presents the evolution of the frequency of the splitted modes as a function of the number N of perfect unit cell between the two defects. In comparison with the result obtained with the equivalent multilayer model (figure 6(b)), the splitted modes present an additional oscillation with respect to the number of unit cell. This oscillation can be correlated to the finite number of unit cells which link the two cavities and produced Fabry-Perot oscillations. The quality factor follows the same behavior than the frequency variation. Here again, as the distance between the two cavities increase, the transmission of the mode is not efficient after only a few μm and the modulation cannot be obtained anymore. Contrariwise, the figure 7(b) presents the case when the two cavities are connected through the straight phononic nanobeam. We can see that the two cavity modes (red dashed line and black solid lines) are transmitted over a large distance and interact with the phononic waveguide eigenmode, giving the opportunity to tune the frequency. This conclusion is in agreement with the one obtained from the simple equivalent multilayer model.

Figure 7 Evolution of the resonant frequency and the quality factor as a function of the distance between two cavities for the 3D nanobeam structure (a) when the connected phononic waveguide is composed of perfect unit cells (see figure 5(a)) and (b) when the connected phononic waveguide is straight (see figure 5(b))

We analyzed the symmetry of the involved modes from the spatial distribution of the longitudinal (u_x) and transverse (u_y) displacement components of the elastic field (figure 8). The perpendicular component (u_z) is not represented here because of its low value, almost at rest.

The first calculation is done for the device composed of the two cavities connected by the corrugated nanobeam (figure 5(a)) at the frequencies $f_A = 2.1578$ GHz and $f_B = 2.1766$ GHz (figure 7). With such distance between the two defects ($N = 3$), we get a strong coupling and two splitted modes appear, respectively symmetric (figure 8(a)) and antisymmetric (figure 8(b)) with respect to the plane in the middle of the structure (black dashed line).

The second set of calculation is realized for the device containing the straight phononic nanobeam connecting the two cavities (figure 5(b)). We chose to represent the displacement fields for a length $D = 1.04$ μm of the phononic waveguide at the frequencies $f_C = 2.049$ GHz, $f_D = 2.058$ GHz, $f_E = 2.058$ GHz for which three separated modes can be distinguished. Two of them (C and D) represented through the snapshot of figure 8(c) and (d) come respectively from the summation and the difference between the cavity and the standing waveguide eigenmodes. The third one represented figure 8(e) does not interact with the phononic eigen mode and keep its antisymmetric character.

Figure 8 (a, b) Spatial distribution of the longitudinal (u_x) and transverse (u_y) displacement components at the frequencies $f_A = 2.042$ GHz and $f_B = 2.062$ GHz, when the two cavity modes are strongly coupled through the connected phononic waveguide is composed of three perfect unit cells. **(c, d, e)** Spatial distribution of the longitudinal (u_x) and transverse (u_y) displacement components at the frequencies $f_C = 2.049$ GHz, $f_D = 2.058$ GHz, and $f_E = 2.052$ GHz when the two cavity modes are coupled through the straight phononic waveguide of length $D = 1.04 \mu\text{m}$.

3. Conclusions

In this work, we have investigated theoretically the coupling of two phononic cavities and their interfacing through a phononic waveguide for coherent control of the elastic waves. This work has been performed through a simple equivalent multilayer method and extended to real three-dimensional structures with the help of finite element method. We first design the phononic cavity inside a phononic silicon nanobeam which combines symmetric stubs grafted on each side and circular holes drilled in the middle. Appropriate choices of the geometrical parameters of the cavity allowed us to confine the elastic waves with high Q -factor. We then investigated the possibility of coupling two identical cavities together, first considering the connection through perfect unit cells of stubs and holes. We find that we were able to couple the two cavity modes which split in two antisymmetric and symmetric modes. We showed that playing with the number of unit cells

between the cavities allowed us to tune and control the frequency and the quality factors of the symmetric and antisymmetric modes. However, increasing the distance between the two cavities quickly decrease the interaction, and even more the transmission of the cavity modes. We then proposed to connect the two cavities through a phononic straight waveguide and showed that a coupling can be achieved between the eigenmodes of the standing phononic waveguide and the cavity modes of same symmetry. With such a property, we have been able to predict theoretically the routing of the cavity modes together with the control and the modulation of their frequencies and quality factors over a large distance separating the two cavities. This work represents a progress in the chip based cavity optomechanical devices for further applications in sensing, metrology, and quantum information science.

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